

Parental Involvement and Peer Support as Predictors of Prosocial Behavior Among Public Junior High School Students

¹Jespir C. Parilla, ²Luningning D. Viterbo

¹Bangcud National High School, ²University of the Immaculate Conception

¹jespir.parilla@deped.gov.ph, ²lviterbo@uic.edu.ph

Article Details:

Received: 16 April 2026

Revised: 18 April 2026

Accepted: 20 April 2026

Published: 25 April 2026

Corresponding Email:

jespir.parilla@deped.gov.ph

Recommended Citation:

Parilla, J. C., Viterbo, L. D. (2026). Parental Involvement and Peer Support as Predictors of Prosocial Behavior Among Public Junior High School Students. *The International Review of Multidisciplinary Research*. 1 (4), 357-368.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19762304>

Index Terms:

values education, parental involvement, peer support, prosocial behavior, junior high school students, descriptive-correlational, Philippines

Abstract. This study aimed to determine the influence of parental involvement and peer support on the prosocial behavior of public junior high school students in Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, Region X. Specifically, it examined the levels of parental involvement, peer support, and prosocial behavior, as well as the relationships and predictive influence among these variables. A quantitative research design employing the descriptive-correlational method was utilized to analyze naturally occurring relationships without manipulation of variables. Data were gathered from junior high school students using adapted, validated, and pilot-tested survey instruments designed to measure parental involvement, peer support, and prosocial behavior. Statistical analyses included mean and standard deviation to determine the level of each variable, Pearson product-moment correlation to examine the relationships among variables, and multiple regression analysis to identify significant predictors of prosocial behavior. Results revealed that parental involvement, peer support, and prosocial behavior were consistently rated at a high level, indicating that these constructs are frequently experienced, manifested, and observed among junior high school students. Correlation analysis showed that both parental involvement and peer support had significant positive relationships with prosocial behavior, with peer support demonstrating a stronger association. Furthermore, multiple regression analysis revealed that peer support emerged as a significant predictor of prosocial behavior, while parental involvement did not register a significant unique predictive influence when analyzed concurrently with peer support. These findings suggest that although parental involvement remains positively associated with adolescents' prosocial behavior, peer relationships exert a more substantial and direct influence on the development of prosocial tendencies among junior high school students. The results underscore the importance of strengthening peer-based support structures in promoting prosocial behavior during adolescence.

Introduction

Prosocial behavior, as demonstrated in acts of helping, sharing, cooperation, and empathy, forms a crucial part of adolescents' social, moral, and emotional development. Such prosocial behaviors play a vital role in creating healthy peer relations and facilitating successful school adjustment, overall psychological well-being, and moral identity of young people (Affuso et al., 2024; Carlo et al., 2022). Although prosocial behavior has been identified as essential in adolescents' lives, current research findings in the field raise concerns regarding its possible deterioration or inconsistency among young people, especially in times of sociopolitical turbulence and increasing academic and psychological pressures (Fitzpatrick & Boers, 2022; Serrano et al., 2023).

The global literature reveals that prosocial behavior tends to diminish during adolescence due to growing peer influences, academic stressors, and other psychological factors (Lansford et al., 2024; Reimann et al., 2024). School-related stresses, peer bullying, and increasing contact with digital media have been linked to declining levels of empathy, cooperation, and helping in adolescents (Morishima et al., 2025; Worley & Meter, 2025). In the Philippines, the same problems have been

identified, particularly within the public secondary education setting amid school closures, mental health issues, and reduced physical interaction among adolescents (Villafania, 2023; Ocampo et al., 2024). Additionally, recent studies carried out among adolescents in Mindanao show that academic pressures, inadequate social networks, and poor community engagement may hinder their empathic responses and prosocial attitudes (Gasas & Luzano, 2024; Baria & Gomez, 2022).

Among socialization factors mentioned in the literature as important for fostering prosocial behavior are parents and peers. Research studies demonstrate that the engagement of parents in adolescents' socialization in the form of affective parenting, open communication, academic assistance, and moral exemplification positively impacts the latter's level of empathy, self-control, and prosociality (Backman et al., 2024; Liu & Wang, 2024; Silletti et al., 2023). Emotionally secure and consistent parent-child relationships promote moral internalization and thus help lay the foundations for other-oriented behaviors (He et al., 2023). On the other hand, peer support significantly contributes to the daily experience of young people, serving as an immediate source of practicing and encouraging prosocial behavior (Brass et al., 2024; García-Moya et al., 2023; Martinot et al., 2022).

While there has been a significant body of research on the impact of parental involvement and peer support on adolescent development, a number of critical gaps need to be addressed. First of all, the literature lacks studies investigating their combined effects on adolescents' prosocial behavior, particularly within collectivist societies like the Philippines. Second, most research has been concentrated on high-income or urban settings, leaving no enough evidence concerning public secondary education in Mindanao, Bukidnon in particular. Finally, most scholars tend to consider prosociality as a unidimensional concept without sufficient focus on affective and behavioral dimensions of prosocial behavior. All this limits the applicability of available studies to specific contexts and hinders the implementation of evidence-based interventions to foster prosociality among Filipino adolescents.

Recognizing the developmental significance of peer interactions and the lasting influence of parental morals on young people, the investigation of the interplay between parental involvement and peer support in shaping their prosocial behavior is both timely and necessary. Given the emphasis of Values Education on moral and social development of adolescents alongside with academic achievements, addressing this gap is critically important. Hence, this study aims to explore the influence of parental involvement and peer support on prosocial behavior of public junior high school students in Malaybalay City, Bukidnon.

Methodology

This study determined the influence of parental involvement and peer support on the prosocial behavior of public junior high school students in Malaybalay City, Bukidnon during the School Year 2025–2026 through the quantitative descriptive-correlational research design.

The quantitative-descriptive approach was utilized to determine the level of parental involvement in terms of emotional support, communication, academic guidance, and moral modeling; the level of peer support in terms of emotional, instrumental, informational, companionship support, and validation; and the level of prosocial behavior of students in terms of prosocial actions and prosocial feelings. The correlational method was employed to determine the significant relationship between parental involvement, peer support, and prosocial behavior. Moreover, multiple regression analysis was used to determine whether parental involvement and peer support significantly influence prosocial behavior among junior high school students.

Results and Discussion

Level of Parental Involvement of Junior High School Students

Presented in table 1 is the overall mean score on parental involvement comes out to be 4.15, which falls into the category of high. In other words, parental involvement in case of junior high school students is quite common. This means that parents are actively participating in the lives of their kids and making sure that things work for the best, though not at the peak level in every aspect. In actuality, this reflects the fact that parents make sure that kids get adequate emotional support, open channels of communication are maintained, advice regarding academics is offered, and positive behaviors are practiced. In turn, students become confident, responsible and value-driven due to this kind of involvement by parents.

The data are presented in Tables 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5

	Mean	SD	Description
Emotional support			
As a student...			
I observe that my parent always supports my interests, including my talent and skills enhancement.	4.42	0.76	Very High
I feel appreciated by my parent for whatever accomplishments I achieve, whether academic or non-academic.	4.09	0.87	High
I observe that my parent is always there for me even when sacrifices are needed.	4.23	0.89	Very High
I observe that even when busy with work, my parent gives me full attention.	4.22	0.85	Very High
I observe that my parent is loving to me but also serves as a disciplinarian when needed.	4.34	0.85	Very High
Category Mean	4.26	0.55	Very High
Communication			
As a student...			
I observe that my parent respects and listens to my opinions or ideas and helps me understand things clearly.	4.08	0.94	High
I observe that my parent makes sure we have bonding time, especially during study or reading time.	4.09	0.89	High
I observe that my parent always communicates with me before I go to school.	3.94	0.97	High
I observe that my parent usually asks me what I did in school when I arrive home.	4.08	0.97	High
Category Mean	4.05	0.71	High
Academic guidance			
As a student...			
I observe that my parent monitors my growth to help me become responsible, confident, and humble.	4.02	1.00	High
I observe that my parent trusts and encourages me to do my tasks in school and at home, including chores and routines, and to take time to relax or play.	4.04	0.92	High
I observe that my parent trained me to become independent so I can easily adjust to changes in school.	4.06	0.98	High
I observe that my parent provides me with technology and learning materials that help boost my creativity and thinking skills.	4.18	0.91	High
Category Mean	4.07	0.73	High
Moral modeling			
As a student...			
I observe that my parent gives support to my teacher to help me improve and develop confidence in my tasks.	4.00	0.92	High
I observe that my parent guides me to maintain good behavior and responsibilities at home and in school.	4.44	3.35	Very High
Category Mean	4.22	1.80	Very High
Overall Mean	4.15	0.67	High

Table 1. Level of Parental Involvement

Emotional Support. The emotional support dimension obtained a category mean of 4.26 and is therefore described as very high. This indicates that parental involvement in terms of emotional support was always evident among the junior high school students. The item means in this category ranged from 4.09 to 4.42. The highest mean score, showing consistent support for students' interests, talents, and skills (\bar{x} = 4.42), reflects parents' strong tendency to encourage and nurture their children's personal development. Meanwhile, the lowest mean score, expressing appreciation for students' accomplishments, whether academic or non-academic (\bar{x} = 4.09), although still described as high, suggests that explicit acknowledgment of achievements was comparatively less emphasized than other expressions of emotional support. Overall, the very high category mean indicates that parents generally manifested warmth, presence, attentiveness, and

affection. The relatively low standard deviation (SD = 0.55) further suggests that students shared similar perceptions regarding the emotional support provided by their parents.

Communication. This dimension obtained a category mean of 4.05 and is therefore described as high. This indicates that parental involvement in terms of communication was oftentimes evident among the junior high school students. The item means in this category ranged from 3.94 to 4.09. The highest mean score, making time for parent–child bonding, especially during study or reading time ($\bar{x} = 4.09$), reflects parents’ deliberate efforts to engage in meaningful interactions and strengthen communication within the household. In contrast, the lowest mean score, communicating with students before they go to school ($\bar{x} = 3.94$), although still described as high, suggests that communication during early morning routines may be slightly less emphasized compared to other interaction opportunities. Overall, these findings indicate that while parent–child communication is generally frequent and positive, certain moments of interaction vary in emphasis across daily contexts.

Academic Guidance. This dimension obtained a category mean of 4.07 and is therefore described as high. This indicates that parental involvement in terms of academic guidance was oftentimes evident among the junior high school students. The item means in this category ranged from 4.02 to 4.18. The highest mean score, providing technology and learning materials that help boost creativity and thinking skills ($\bar{x} = 4.18$), reflects parents’ strong commitment to supporting learning by equipping their children with appropriate academic resources. In contrast, the lowest mean score, monitoring students’ growth to help them become responsible, confident, and humble ($\bar{x} = 4.02$), although still described as high, suggests that developmental monitoring is slightly less emphasized compared to resource provision and instructional support. Overall, these findings indicate that parents generally provide consistent academic guidance, with some variation in emphasis across different forms of support.

Moral modeling. This dimension obtained a category mean of 4.22 and is therefore described as very high. This indicates that parental involvement in terms of moral modeling was always evident among the junior high school students. The item means in this category ranged from 4.00 to 4.44. The highest mean score, guiding students to maintain good behavior and responsibilities at home and in school ($\bar{x} = 4.44$), reflects parents’ consistent efforts to model appropriate conduct and reinforce responsible behavior across daily settings. In contrast, the lowest mean score, giving support to teachers to help improve and develop students’ confidence in their tasks ($\bar{x} = 4.00$), although still described as high, suggests that direct parental collaboration with teachers may be slightly less emphasized compared to home-based moral guidance. Overall, these findings indicate that parents consistently serve as moral exemplars for their children, with some variation in how moral support is expressed across school-related and home-based contexts.

Level of Peer Support of Junior High School Students

Presented in Table 2 is the overall mean of peer support, which is 3.88 and is therefore described as high. This implies that peer support among junior high school students is oftentimes evident. This means that students generally experience positive and supportive relationships with their classmates, although peer support may not always be present at the highest possible level in all situations.

Emotional support As a student...	Mean	SD	Description
I believe that peer support helps build my confidence in the classroom.	4.00	0.83	High
I believe that with my classmates’ help, I feel less worried about my academic performance.	3.95	0.92	High
I believe that with my peers’ support, my self-esteem becomes stronger.	3.90	0.93	High
I believe that my peers help me feel emotionally secure in my learning.	3.87	1.00	High
I believe that peer support helps me feel that I belong in my learning community.	3.82	0.87	High
I believe that my classmates’ friendship helps me feel accepted by others.	3.86	0.90	High
Category Mean	3.90	0.64	High

Instrumental support			
As a student...			
I believe that my classmates offer resources that help me pay more attention to our learning materials.	3.78	0.91	High
I believe that my classmates give practical help that supports me in achieving good school outcomes.	3.77	0.92	High
I believe that with my classmates' support, I am more encouraged to study well and reach my school goals.	3.76	0.95	High
I believe that my peers' support helps me build positive relationships with my classmates.	3.78	0.90	High
Category Mean	3.77	0.69	High
Informational support			
As a student...			
I believe that peer support helps improve my knowledge and my performance in school.	3.79	0.89	High
I believe that peer support makes me more active in my studies.	3.81	0.90	High
I believe that when my classmates help me, I gain the knowledge I need to overcome academic challenges.	3.86	0.92	High
When my classmates give advice, I become more prepared to use better learning strategies.	3.86	0.84	High
Peer feedback helps make learning faster and more effective.	3.78	0.94	High
Peer feedback helps improve my critical thinking skills.	3.89	0.88	High
Peer support helps us share knowledge with one another.	3.96	0.82	High
Category Mean	3.85	0.64	High
Companionship support			
As a student...			
I believe that peer feedback helps us cooperate and create a positive learning environment.	3.92	0.82	High
peer support helps us learn from one another.	3.94	0.84	High
peer support builds relationships based on trust and respect.	4.02	0.82	High
Category Mean	3.96	0.65	High
Validation			
As a student...			
I believe that peer support helps me develop my academic identity.	3.89	0.82	High
I believe that peer support helps me develop a more positive attitude toward my schoolwork and the school environment.	3.94	0.82	High
Category Mean	3.91	0.69	High
Overall Mean	3.88	0.52	High

Table 2. Level of Peer Support

Practically, this indicates that peers frequently provide emotional encouragement, practical assistance, information sharing, companionship, and affirmation, helping students feel accepted and supported in their school environment. Students often feel understood and valued by their peers, which contributes to a sense of belonging and shared responsibility within the group. The standard deviation of 0.52 means that peer support experiences are clustered around the average, indicating that most students have relatively similar experiences in terms of the support they receive from their peers.

Emotional Support. The emotional support dimension obtained a category mean of 3.90 and is therefore described as high. This indicates that peer emotional support was oftentimes evident among the junior high school students. The item means in this category ranged from 3.82 to 4.00. The highest mean score, helping build confidence in the classroom ($\bar{x} = 4.00$), reflects peers' strong role in encouraging self-confidence and active participation in learning activities. In contrast, the lowest mean score, helping students feel that they belong to their learning community ($\bar{x} = 3.82$), although still described as high, suggests that feelings of group belonging were slightly less emphasized than direct emotional encouragement. Overall, the high category mean indicates that classmates commonly provide reassurance, encouragement, acceptance, and emotional comfort. The standard deviation ($SD = 0.64$) further suggests that students shared relatively similar perceptions regarding the emotional support they received from their peers.

Instrumental support. The instrumental support dimension obtained a category mean of 3.77 and is therefore described as high. This indicates that peer instrumental support was oftentimes evident among the junior high school students. The item means in this category ranged from 3.76 to 3.78. The highest mean score, offering resources that help students focus on learning materials ($\bar{x} = 3.78$), reflects peers' active role in providing concrete assistance for academic tasks. In contrast, the lowest mean score, encouraging students to study well and reach their school goals ($\bar{x} = 3.76$), although still described as high, suggests that motivational assistance is slightly less emphasized than direct, task-based help. Overall, the high category mean indicates that classmates commonly provide practical support, shared resources, and assistance that facilitate learning activities. The standard deviation ($SD = 0.69$) further suggests that students shared relatively similar perceptions regarding the instrumental support they received from their peers.

The High level of instrumental peer support implies that students benefit from an environment where classmates regularly help each other manage school tasks, understand academic content, and stay motivated. This type of support enhances academic adjustment, increases problem-solving skills, and strengthens collaborative learning habits. It also builds a sense of shared responsibility and teamwork, which are essential for both academic success and prosocial development. The moderate consistency of scores suggests that instrumental support is widely practiced across the student population, contributing to a supportive academic culture in which peers serve as dependable partners in learning.

The present results showing a high level of instrumental peer support can be linked to the work of Karamina and Martani (2023), who described how junior high school students often receive instrumental support from their peers. In their study, instrumental support was demonstrated when other students provided learning material and helped peers complete assignments while assisting them to meet the academic requirements of the courses taken. Thus, all these aspects correlate well with the present findings, especially provision of resources needed to learn, assistance in getting scholarly results, and helping peers meet academic demands.

Like in this research, Shao et al. (2024) found that in their descriptive study, junior high school students had mutual academic assistance with classmates, task-related support, and cooperative behaviors within the classroom environment. As in this paper, such support was shown when peers collaborated together in performing specific tasks and learning, sharing resources needed to learn new information, and cooperating in order to accomplish some school assignments. Taken together, these findings support the conclusion about instrumental peer support as a common phenomenon among junior high school students.

On the contrary, the findings of Worley and Meter (2025) indicate low levels of instrumental peer support, as described by these authors' descriptive study. The researchers showed that students, who were victims of bullying and violence among peers, received minimal practical assistance, had limited academic resources, and poor task-related cooperation with other peers. However, the present results contradict these findings as junior high school students regularly receive practical help, share academic resources, and have help in completing school tasks as indicated by a higher mean category of instrumental support.

Informational support. The informational support dimension obtained a category mean of 3.85 and is therefore described as high. This indicates that peer informational support was oftentimes evident among the junior high school students. The item means in this category ranged from 3.78 to 3.96. The highest mean score, sharing knowledge with one another ($\bar{x} = 3.96$), reflects peers' active role in exchanging explanations and academic information. In contrast, the lowest mean score, peer feedback helping students learn faster and more effectively ($\bar{x} = 3.78$), although still described as high, suggests that feedback is slightly less emphasized than direct advice and knowledge sharing. Overall, the high category mean indicates that classmates commonly provide guidance, explanations, and learning strategies to support one another. The standard deviation ($SD = 0.64$) further suggests that students shared relatively similar perceptions regarding the informational support they received from their peers.

Companionship support. The companionship support dimension obtained a category mean of 3.96 and is therefore described as high. This indicates that peer companionship was oftentimes evident among the junior high school students. The item means in this category ranged from 3.92 to 4.02. The highest mean score, building relationships based on trust and respect ($\bar{x} = 4.02$), reflects the presence of strong and supportive peer relationships. In contrast, the lowest mean score, peer feedback helping create a positive learning environment ($\bar{x} = 3.92$), although still described as high, suggests that companionship is slightly more evident in interpersonal relationships than in influencing the overall learning environment. Overall, the high category mean indicates that students commonly experience companionship through shared activities, cooperation, and stable friendships. The standard deviation ($SD = 0.65$) further suggests that students shared relatively similar perceptions regarding the companionship support they received from their peers.

Validation Support. The validation support dimension obtained a category mean of 3.91 and is therefore described as high. This indicates that peer validation was oftentimes evident among the junior high school students. The item means in this

category ranged from 3.89 to 3.94. The highest mean score, fostering a more positive attitude toward schoolwork and the school environment ($\bar{x} = 3.94$), reflects peers' role in affirming students' efforts and encouraging a positive academic outlook. In contrast, the lowest mean score, helping students develop their academic identity ($\bar{x} = 3.89$), although still described as high, suggests that identity-related validation is slightly less emphasized than general encouragement toward school activities. Overall, the high category mean indicates that students commonly experience affirmation, encouragement, and positive recognition from their peers. The standard deviation ($SD = 0.69$) further suggests that students shared relatively similar perceptions regarding the validation support they received from their classmates.

Level of Prosocial Behavior of Junior High School Students

Presented in Table 3 is the overall mean of prosocial behavior, which is 4.04 and is therefore described as high. This implies that prosocial behavior among junior high school students is oftentimes demonstrated. This means that students generally engage in positive social actions toward others, although not always at the highest level in all situations. Practically, this indicates that students frequently help classmates, share resources, cooperate in group activities, and comfort peers in distress, reflecting concern and responsiveness toward others. The relatively low standard deviation ($SD = 0.50$) indicates that these behaviors are closely clustered around the mean, suggesting that most students display similar levels of prosocial tendencies within the school community. help create a supportive school climate where students feel safe, accepted, and emotionally connected. High prosociality also strengthens emotional resilience, enhances conflict resolution skills, and promotes healthier relationships. The consistency of scores indicates that these prosocial tendencies are widespread across students, suggesting that the school environment encourages kindness, collaboration, and helpfulness as part of students' daily interactions.

Prosocial Actions As a student...	Mean	SD	Description
I am happy to help my friends with their activities.	4.16	0.76	High
I share the things I have with my friends.	4.02	0.81	High
I try my best to help others.	4.06	0.81	High
I join volunteer activities to help people who are in need.	3.90	0.86	High
I help people right away when they need assistance.	3.97	0.82	High
I do what I can to help others avoid getting into trouble.	3.98	0.82	High
I am willing to share my knowledge and abilities with others.	4.04	0.82	High
I try to comfort my friends when they are sad.	4.00	0.84	High
I easily lend money or other things to my friends.	3.87	0.90	High
I try to stay close to and take care of friends who need help.	3.97	0.86	High
I quickly share any good opportunity that comes to me with my friends.	4.02	0.80	High
I spend time with friends who feel lonely.	4.04	0.81	High
Category Mean	3.99	0.53	High
Prosocial feelings As a student...			
I feel empathy for people who are in need.	4.16	0.79	High
I can strongly feel what others feel.	4.03	0.80	High
I can easily put myself in the shoes of people who are uncomfortable or struggling.	4.00	0.84	High
I can sense when my friends feel uncomfortable, even if they don't tell me directly.	4.13	0.86	High
Category Mean	4.08	0.59	High
Overall Mean	4.04	0.50	High

Table 3. Level of Prosocial Behavior

Prosocial Actions. The prosocial actions dimension obtained a category mean of 3.99 and is therefore described as high. This indicates that prosocial behavior was oftentimes demonstrated among the junior high school students. The item means in this category ranged from 3.87 to 4.16. The highest mean score, helping friends with their activities ($\bar{x} = 4.16$), reflects students' strong willingness to assist classmates. In contrast, the lowest mean score, lending money or other things to friends ($\bar{x} = 3.87$), although still described as high, suggests that material assistance is slightly less emphasized than direct help and participation. Overall, the high category mean indicates that students commonly engage in helping, sharing,

cooperation, and caring behaviors during daily school interactions. The standard deviation (SD = 0.53) further suggests that students shared relatively similar levels of engagement in prosocial actions.

Prosocial feelings. The prosocial feelings dimension obtained a category mean of 4.08 and is therefore described as high. This indicates that prosocial feelings were oftentimes demonstrated among the junior high school students. The item means in this category ranged from 4.00 to 4.16. The highest mean score, feeling empathy for people in need ($\bar{x} = 4.16$), reflects students' strong empathic concern for others, while sensing friends' discomfort even without verbal cues ($\bar{x} = 4.13$) highlights their emotional awareness. In contrast, the lowest mean score, putting oneself in others' shoes ($\bar{x} = 4.00$), although still high, suggests that perspective-taking is slightly less emphasized than emotional sensitivity. Overall, the high category mean indicates that students commonly experience empathy and emotional responsiveness toward others. The standard deviation (SD = 0.59) further suggests that students shared relatively similar levels of prosocial feelings.

Significance of the Relationship of Parental Involvement, Peer Support, and Prosocial Behavior

The correlation results in Table 4 show that both parental involvement and peer support are significantly correlated to prosocial behavior. Parental involvement ($r = 0.344, p < .001$) demonstrates a moderate positive relationship, indicating that adolescents with more supportive, communicative, and morally engaged parents tend to show stronger prosocial behaviors. Meanwhile, peer support ($r = 0.658, p < .001$) are significantly correlated to prosocial behavior, indicating a stronger positive relationship, suggesting that adolescents who experience acceptance, companionship, and encouragement from peers are even more likely to help, cooperate, and show empathy.

Variables	Prosocial Behavior		
	r - value	p-value	Remarks
Parental Involvement	0.344	< .001	Significant
Peer Support	0.658	< .001	Significant

Table 4. Significance of the Relationship of Parental Involvement, Peer Support, and Prosocial Behavior

The findings indicate that parental involvement has a significant moderate positive relationship with prosocial behavior. This suggests that adolescents who experience emotional support, open communication, guidance, and moral modeling at home are more likely to demonstrate helping, sharing, cooperation, and empathy. While the strength of the relationship is moderate, parental involvement remains an important foundation in shaping adolescents' moral orientation, emotional regulation, and responsible behavior. However, the magnitude of the relationship also implies that adolescents' prosocial development is influenced by social contexts beyond the family.

In contrast, peer support shows a strong and significant positive relationship with prosocial behavior, highlighting the central role of peers during adolescence. Students who receive emotional reassurance, companionship, validation, informational guidance, and practical assistance from peers are more likely to engage in prosocial actions and express prosocial feelings. The stronger association indicates that daily peer interactions provide immediate opportunities for practicing empathy, cooperation, and helping behaviors, making peers a primary influence on prosocial development at this stage.

Taken together, the findings show that both parental involvement and peer support contribute to prosocial behavior, though in different capacities. Parental involvement appears to function as a foundational influence that supports moral and emotional development, whereas peer support exerts a more direct and immediate impact on prosocial behavior. This underscores the importance of fostering supportive peer environments while sustaining positive family engagement to promote empathy, kindness, and socially responsible behavior among junior high school students.

Significance of the Influence of Parental Involvement and Peer Support on Prosocial Behavior

The regression analysis in Table 5 shows that parental involvement and peer support jointly explained 43.50% of the variance in prosocial behavior ($F = 92.953, p < .001$), indicating that together these variables significantly shaped students' prosocial tendencies. Suggesting a substantial joint contribution, while the remaining 56.50% of the variance may be influenced by other personal, social, and contextual factors beyond the scope of this study. However, parental involvement did not significantly influence prosocial behavior on its own ($\beta = 0.062, p = 0.256$).

Variables	β	Prosocial Behavior		
		t	p-value	Remarks
Parental Involvement	0.062	1.139	0.256	Not Significant
Peer Support	0.629	11.508	< .001	Significant
Holistic Model				
r ²	0.435			
F-value	92.953			
p-value	< .001			
Remarks	Significant			

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 5. Significance of the Influence of Parental Involvement and Peer Support on Prosocial Behavior

This suggests that although parents contribute to adolescents' moral and emotional foundations, their influence becomes less direct as adolescents rely more on peer-centered interactions. In contrast, peer support emerged as a strong and significant predictor ($\beta = 0.629, p < .001$), showing that emotional reassurance, companionship, validation, and academic help from peers directly promote prosocial actions and feelings. This aligns with literature noting that peer acceptance, belongingness, and supportive friendships strongly enhance empathy, cooperation, and helping behavior. These results reinforce the developmental pattern that peers become the dominant social influence during adolescence, shaping prosocial behavior more powerfully than parental involvement.

The regression results show that parental involvement does not have a significant unique influence on prosocial behavior when peer support is considered simultaneously. This suggests that while parental involvement contributes to adolescents' emotional security, moral grounding, and self-regulation, its effect on prosocial behavior during adolescence is largely indirect rather than immediate. Parents appear to function as foundational influences who shape values and emotional stability, but do not serve as the primary drivers of day-to-day prosocial actions at this developmental stage. In contrast, peer support emerged as a strong and significant predictor of prosocial behavior, indicating that adolescents who receive emotional reassurance, companionship, validation, guidance, and practical assistance from peers are more likely to demonstrate helping, sharing, cooperation, and empathy. This strong predictive relationship highlights the importance of peers as the most immediate and influential social context in which prosocial behaviors are practiced and reinforced during adolescence.

Taken together, the findings suggest that parental involvement and peer support operate in complementary but distinct ways. Parental involvement provides an underlying moral and emotional foundation established earlier in development, whereas peer support exerts a more direct influence through daily interaction, acceptance, and behavioral reinforcement. This pattern explains why parental involvement contributes to the overall model but does not independently predict prosocial behavior, while peer support emerges as the dominant predictor.

These findings are consistent with Social Learning Theory, which proposes that behavior is acquired through observation, interaction, and reinforcement within socially meaningful contexts. The prominence of peer support reflects the relevance and proximity of peers as behavioral models during adolescence. Frequent peer interactions create continuous opportunities for observing and reinforcing prosocial actions, such as cooperation and empathy. Meanwhile, parental influence remains important but functions primarily as an indirect moral and emotional base rather than an immediate source of behavioral modeling.

Overall, the results emphasize that prosocial behavior in adolescence is primarily shaped within peer contexts, supported by the foundational role of family socialization, underscoring the importance of fostering positive peer environments alongside sustained parental engagement.

Peer Support as a Significant Predictor of Prosocial Behavior

Peer support emerges as a very reliable and statistically significant predictor of prosocial behavior ($\beta = 0.629, p < .001$) according to the regression analysis presented. In other words, adolescents who receive psychological comfort, company,

acknowledgment, guidance, and physical aid from peers are more prone to demonstrate helping, sharing, cooperativeness, and consolation behavior. The effect can be viewed as considerable enough because adolescents rely on peers for their social needs to form identity and reinforce behaviors in order to develop empathy and prosocial tendencies.

Parental Involvement as a Non-Significant Predictor of Prosocial Behavior

According to the regression analysis, parental involvement does not significantly predict prosocial behavior among junior high school students when peer support is included in the model ($\beta = 0.062$, $p = 0.256$). This indicates that although parental involvement is associated with prosocial behavior, its influence becomes indirect rather than predictive during adolescence. Parental involvement appears to function as a foundational influence by shaping adolescents' moral values, emotional development, and self-regulation earlier in life, but it does not directly account for variations in prosocial behavior at this stage.

As adolescents progress through junior high school, prosocial behavior becomes more strongly associated with peer interaction. This shift reflects a developmental pattern in which peers assume a more prominent role in guiding social behavior, while parents remain important as underlying sources of moral and emotional support. Thus, parental involvement continues to matter, but its effect operates primarily through internalized values rather than through immediate behavioral influence during adolescence.

Conclusion and Implications

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Parental involvement among public junior high school students is high, indicating that parents actively provide emotional support, communication, academic guidance, and moral modeling.
2. Peer support is high, reflecting frequent emotional, instrumental, informational, companionship, and validation support among students.
3. Prosocial behavior is high, as students commonly demonstrate helping, sharing, cooperation, empathy, and prosocial feelings.
4. Parental involvement and peer support are significantly related to prosocial behavior, with peer support showing a stronger association.
5. Peer support is the strongest predictor of prosocial behavior, suggesting that peers play a more direct role than parents in influencing prosocial behavior during adolescence.

Acknowledgements

The researcher sincerely expresses his gratitude to all individuals whose support, guidance, and encouragement contributed to the successful completion of this study. Foremost appreciation is extended to Dr. Luningning D. Viterbo, thesis adviser, for her expertise, patience, and invaluable guidance throughout the research process. Deep gratitude is also conveyed to the members of the panel, Dr. Avee Joy B. Dayaganon, Dr. Sylvia J. Pidor, Dr. Rhodora S. Gamboa, and Dr. Erick T. Baloran, for their time, insightful comments, and scholarly contributions that strengthened the study.

Sincere thanks are extended to Dr. Cherry Mae Limbaco-Reyes, Schools Division Superintendent of Malaybalay City Division, and to the School Heads, for their support and permission to conduct the research. The researcher also acknowledges the encouragement and camaraderie of his classmates, Sr. Jona and Ma'am Marjorie whose support made the graduate journey meaningful.

Heartfelt gratitude is given to the researcher's parents, Nanay Tata and Tatay Rudy, siblings, and to Julie Mae for their unwavering love, prayers, motivation, and moral support. Appreciation is likewise extended to the student-respondents for their cooperation, and to Dr. Mary Jane B. Amoguis, Dean of the Graduate School, for her leadership and inspiration.

Above all, the researcher offers this work to the Almighty God, for the wisdom, strength, and grace bestowed throughout this academic journey.

Funding

This research received no external funding from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit funding agency, and no organization provided financial support for the conduct of the study, authorship, or publication of this article.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

References

- Affuso, G., Picone, N., De Angelis, G., Dragone, M., Esposito, C., Pannone, M., Zannone, A., & Bacchini, D. (2024). The reciprocal effects of prosociality, peer support, and psychological well-being in adolescence: A four-wave longitudinal study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 21(12), 1630. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/21/12/1630>
- Backman, H., Lahti, K., Laajasalo, T., Kaakinen, M., & Aronen, E. T. (2024). Positive parenting and adolescent prosocial behaviour: A mediation analysis with representative data. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, 29(1), Article 2374426. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/02673843.2024.2374426>
- Baria, K., & Gomez, D. (2022). Influence of social support to student learning and development. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 11(2), 69–97. <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrse.2022.112>
- Brass, N. R., Hung, C., Stephen, T., Bergin, C., Rose, C., & Prewett, S. (2024). Students' and classmates' prosocial behavior predict academic engagement in middle school. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-024-02027-1>
- Carlo, G., Padilla-Walker, L. M., & Nielson, M. G. (2022). Longitudinal bidirectional relations between adolescents' empathy and prosocial behavior. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 51(5), 907–921. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-021-01544-5>
- Cirimele, F., Pastorelli, C., Remondi, C., Zuffianò, A., Thartori, E., Gerbino, M., Di Giunta, L., Bacchini, D., Oburu, P., Skinner, A. T., Sorbring, E., Steinberg, L., Uribe Tirado, L. M., Yotanyamaneewong, S., Peña Alampay, L., Al-Hassan, S. M., Bornstein, M. H., Chang, L., Deater-Deckard, K., Dodge, K. A., Gurdal, S., Junla, D., Eisenberg, N., & Lansford, J. E. (2024). The development of prosocial behavior from late childhood to adolescence: A longitudinal and multicultural study. *Frontiers in Developmental Psychology*, 2, Article 1472589. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fdpys.2024.1472589>
- Fitzpatrick, C., & Boers, E. (2022). Developmental associations between media use and adolescent prosocial behavior. *Health Education & Behavior*, 49(2), 265–271. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10901981211035702>
- García-Moya, I., Brooks, F., Morgan, A., & Moreno, C. (2023). Subjective well-being and peer support in adolescence: The role of social connectedness. *Journal of Adolescence*, 95, 12–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adolescence.2023.01.002>
- Ga-as, V. C. R., & Luzano, J. F. P. (2024). Academic stress and coping mechanisms among high school students: A systematic review. *International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research*, 8(5), 129–132. <http://ijeais.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/5/IJAMR240518.pdf>
- He, L., Tan, C.-S., Pung, P.-W., Hu, J., Tang, H.-B., & Cheng, S.-M. (2023). The role of parental rejection and poverty in the development of prosocial behavior among left-behind adolescents in rural China. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 155, Article 107143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2023.107143>
- Liu, Q., & Wang, Z. (2024). Longitudinal relationships among parenting, prosocial behaviors, and emotional problems: Examining between- and within-person associations in adolescents. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 53, 2669–2682. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-024-02056-w>
- Martinot, D., Sicard, A., Gul, B., Yakimova, S., Taillandier-Schmitt, A., & Maitenant, C. (2022). Peers and teachers as the best source of social support for school engagement for both advantaged and priority education area students. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, Article 958286. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.958286>
- Morishima, R., Usami, S., Kanehara, A., Okada, N., Noguchi, H., Yagishita, S., Fukuda, M., & Kasai, K. (2025). Classroom-level and individual-level prosociality and help-seeking behaviors among adolescents. *JAMA Network Open*, 8(5), e2510319. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2025.10319>
- Silletti, F., Iannello, N. M., Inguglia, S., Inguglia, C., Cassibba, R., Eisner, M., Ribeaud, D., & Musso, P. (2024). Do self-control and parental involvement promote prosociality and hinder internalizing problems? A four-wave longitudinal

- study from early to mid-to-late adolescence. *Journal of Early Adolescence*.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/02724316231210250>
- Villafania, J. B. (2023). Turning challenges into opportunities: Mental health and coping styles among Filipino youth during pandemic towards program and policy development framework. *Arts & Humanities Open Access Journal*, 5(1), 23–31. <https://doi.org/10.15406/ahoaj.2023.05.00183>
- Worley, J. T., Meter, D. J., Ramirez Hall, A., Nishina, A., & Medina, M. A. (2023). Prospective associations between peer support, academic competence, and anxiety in college students. *Social Psychology of Education*, 26, 1017–1035. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37362052/>

Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.